

DVR with Modified Y Source Inverter and MCFC

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Abstract—Power quality is a big challenge nowadays. Various disturbances present in the power system are voltage sag, voltage swell, harmonics, transients, interruptions, voltage collapse etc. To solve the problem of power quality, various custom power devices are generally used in a power system, dynamic voltage restorer (DVR) being one of them. DVR is used for the compensation of voltage sag and swell. In this paper, a model of DVR with molten carbonate fuel cell (MCFC) and Y source inverter is proposed. The proposed model is compared with the existing ones to check its performance characteristics. MATLAB/SIMULINK was been used to check and compare the performance of the proposed with existing models.

Keywords-Y source inverter; DVR; MCFC

I. INTRODUCTION

Most conventional inverters commonly used in power systems are voltage source inverters (VSI) and current source inverters (CSI). These traditional voltage source inverters have two major drawbacks: AC output voltage is less than the DC input voltage, so it is operated only in buck mode, and two switches in the same phase leg cannot turn on simultaneously, since this will create a short-circuit in the system. To overcome these problems impedance network has proven to be more effective and efficient in power conversion between the source and the load over a wide range of electric power applications. Various impedance networks have been proposed with Z-source [1] impedance being the pioneer and prominent network. It has been used in DC-DC [2], DC-AC [3], and AC-AC [4]. In the later stages some modified Z-source inverters were proposed like quasi-Z [5, 6], embedded-Z [7, 8], series-Z [9] etc. Authors in [12] applied Z source inverter in DVR along with molten carbonate fuel cell (MCFC). This improved the performance of the system to a great extent. In this paper, Y source inverter has been used in the DVR with MCFC and its performance has been compared with existing models [10, 11]. The proposed Y-source inverter consists of a DC source, Y-impedance network and pulse width modulation (PWM). The complete model has been simulated in Matlab/Simulink. A comparison between different network topologies based on passive components count is shown in Table I.

II. PROPOSED Y SOURCE INVERTER

The proposed Y-source network in this study has a diode D, two capacitors C1 and C2 and a three winding transformers (W1, W2 and W3), as shown in Figure 1.

TABLE I. COMPARISON TABLE

Name of Inverter	Number of Capacitors	Number of Inductors	Number of Diodes
Z Source	2	2	1
Quasi Z Source	2	2	1
Γ Source	2	1 inductor, 2 windings	1
Trans Z Source	2	1 integrated, 2 windings	1
Y Source	1	1 integrated winding	1

Fig. 1. Proposed Y source inverter.

The proposed Y-source network has a shoot-through and non-shoot-through operation. For shoot-through-operation the circuit is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Circuit for shoot-through operation.

Let V_{W1} be the voltage drop across W1. Then from the circuit of Figure 2 we have:

$$V_d + V_{C1} = V_{C2}$$

$$V_d + V_{C1} = \frac{V_{W1}}{\frac{N_1}{N_3}} - \frac{V_{W1}}{\frac{N_1}{N_2}} = \frac{V_{W1}(N_3 - N_2)}{N_1}$$

or $V_{W1} = \frac{(V_d + V_{C1})N_1}{N_3 - N_2}$ (1)

The circuit for non-shoot-through operation is shown in Figure 3. Let, V_i be the DC link voltage, dsh the shoot through zero state of the inverter and M the modulation index.

with the model of DVR with MCFC, ultra-capacitor and Z source inverter presented in [12]. The system parameters used for testing are given in Table II.

TABLE II. SYSTEM PARAMETERS

Parameters	DVR with Z source inverter [12]	Proposed DVR with Y source inverter
Voltage	120V	120V
Frequency	50Hz	50Hz
Transformer	1KVA	1KVA
Load	R L	R L
DC source	MCFC	MCFC
Type of inverter	Z sourced	Y sourced
Filter	R=0.4Ω, L=3mH, C=25μF	R=1.3Ω, L=38mH, C=195μF

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

The profile of supply voltage, load injected voltage and load voltage of the new proposed DVR with Y source inverter and MCFC is shown in Figure 7. The profile of the new proposed DVR for single phase sag and swell is shown in Figure 8. The profile of the new proposed DVR for three phase sag and swell is shown in Figure 9. The comparison of the proposed DVR with Y source inverter and the DVR model of [12] is given in Table III. The THD analysis of the model in [12] is shown in Figure 10 and the THD analysis of the proposed model is shown in Figure 11.

Fig. 7. Profile of proposed DVR with Y source inverter.

Fig. 8. Single phase sag and swell profile of proposed DVR.

Fig. 9. Three phase sag and swell profile of proposed DVR.

TABLE III. COMPARISON TABLE

Percentage of voltage sag	DVR with Z source inverter [12]	Proposed DVR with Y source inverter
	Percentage of THD in DVR injected voltage	Percentage of THD in DVR injected voltage
10	1.5	0.58
30	2.4	0.63
50	2.3	0.72
70	2.2	0.79
90	2.1	0.67

Fig. 10. THD analysis of the model of [12]

Fig. 11. THD Analysis of proposed model with Y source inverter

VI. CONCLUSION

The proposed model has been simulated in Matlab/Simulink and gave good convergence with ode23s. But the speed of simulation was observed to be very slow. The proposed inverter has more circuit elements which makes it more complicated. It has been observed that in Y-source inverter voltage gain is very high when operated at higher modulation index. The proposed DVR is capable of injecting appropriate voltages even when the system is subjected to deep voltage sags, without the need to have an energy source of higher rating. The proposed DVR performs robustly with reduced THD in the load voltage while keeping the stored

energy requirement low. From the above analysis it is clear that MCFC based DVR with fuzzy control is the most efficient device for the improvement of power quality in the power system. The THD level of the proposed model was found to be low compared with the model proposed in [12]. The proposed model is thus much better in comparison with the model in [12].

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Z. Peng, "Z-source inverter", IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications, Vol. 2, No. 39, pp. 504-510, 2003
- [2] H. Cha, F. Z. Peng, D. W. Yoo, "Distributed impedance network (Z network) dc-dc converter", IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics, Vol. 11, No. 25, pp. 2722-2733, 2010
- [3] Y. Tang, S. Xie, C. Zhang, "Z-source ac-ac converters solving commutation problem", IEEE Transaction on Power Electronics, Vol. 2, No. 22, pp. 2146-2154, 2007
- [4] X. P. Fang, Z. M. Qian, F. Z. Peng, "Single-phase Z-source PWM ac-ac converters", IEEE Power Electronics Letters, Vol. 4, No. 3, pp. 121-124, 2005
- [5] J. Anderson, F. Z. Peng, "Four quasi-Z-source inverters", 2008 IEEE Power Electronics Specialists Conference, Rhodes, Greece, August 8, 2008
- [6] P. C. Loh, F. Gao, F. Blaabjerg, A. L. Goh, "Buck-Boost Impedance Networks", 2007 European Conference on Power Electronics and Applications, Aalborg, Denmark, January 4, 2008
- [7] J. Anderson, F. Z. Peng, "A class of quasi-Z-source inverters", 2008 IEEE Industry Applications Society Annual Meeting, Edmonton, Canada, October 5-9, 2008
- [8] P. C. Loh, F. Gao, F. Blaabjerg, "Embedded EZ-source inverters", IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications, Vol. 46, No. 1, pp. 256-267, 2010
- [9] Y. Tang, S. Xie, C. Zhang, "An improved Z-source inverter", IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics, Vol. 26, No. 12, pp. 3865-3868, 2011
- [10] C. Bharatiraja, S. Jeevananthan, R. Latha, "FPGA based practical implementation of NPC-MLI with SVPWM for an autonomous operation PV system with capacitor balancing", International Journal of Electrical Power and Energy Systems, Vol. 61, No. 1, pp. 489-509, 2014
- [11] G. Prakash, C. Subramani, C. Bharatiraja, M. Shabin, "A low cost single phase grid connected reduced switch PV inverter based on time frame switching scheme", International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems, Vol. 77, pp. 100-111, 2016
- [12] J. Chakravorty, G. Sharma, V. Bhatia, "Analysis of a DVR with Molten Carbonate Fuel Cell and Fuzzy Logic Control", Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research, Vol. 8, No. 2, pp. 2673-2679, 2018
- [13] J. Milewski, A. Miller, "Influences of the type and thickness of electrolyte on solid oxide fuel cell hybrid system performance", Journal of Fuel Cell Science and Technology, Vol. 3, No. 4, pp. 396-402, 2006